

Survey of storage insect pests on wheat varieties at Arsi and West Arsi, South Eastern Ethiopia

*Shumi Regassa Gameda

Crop protection Research at Kulumsa Agricultural Research center, Ethiopian Agricultural Research institute, Addis Ababa Ethiopia.

***Corresponding author: Shumi Regassa Gameda**

Crop protection Research at Kulumsa Agricultural Research center, Ethiopian Agricultural Research institute, Addis Ababa Ethiopia.

Abstract

Insects are animals that have an external skeleton (exoskeleton), three body sections (head, thorax, and abdomen) and three pairs of legs, typically two pairs of wings in the adult stage, compound eyes, and antennae. Most stored-product insect pests are either beetles (Coleoptera) or moths (Lepidoptera), although there are exceptions, such as psocids, that don't fall in these two groups. Pest survey is an official procedure conducted over a defined period of time to determine the characteristics of a pest population or to determine which pest species occur in an area. Post-harvest losses occur at different points (harvesting, drying, threshing, winnowing, transportation and storage. Factors responsible for poor grain storage; -Poor storage structures (stores) or location, Inadequate drying, Pests, Inadequate knowledge on good storage practices, Poor store management and Weather and other natural causes. The present study done using a semi-structured questionnaire survey in 2019 at Arsi and West Arsi, south Eastern Ethiopia reported losses on stored wheat along on the different post-harvest operations to be between 12 and 24%, the average being 18%. Even though losses occur at any time from harvest to consumption, higher loss figure was reported when there was rain at harvest. Therefore, great focus must be given to pre- and post-harvest losses to address quality wheat seed for end users.

Keywords: Survey, insect pest, pre- and post-harvest losses, storage quality, wheat.

Introduction

In many African countries, the post-harvest losses of food cereals are estimated at 25% of the total crop harvested. For some crops such as fruits, vegetables and root crops, being less hardy than cereals, post-harvest losses can reach 50% (Voices Newsletter, 2006). In East Africa and the Near East, economic losses in the dairy sector due to spoilage and waste could average as much as US\$90 million/year (FAO, 2004). The causes of food losses and waste in low-income countries are mainly connected to financial, managerial and technical limitations in harvesting techniques, storage and cooling facilities in difficult climatic conditions, infrastructure, packaging and marketing systems. Given that many smallholder farmers in developing countries live on the margins of food insecurity, a reduction in food losses could have an immediate and significant impact on their livelihoods (The World Bank *et al.*, 2011). In Ethiopia Desalegn *et al.* (2017) studied 14 top wheat-producing areas in three agro-ecologies (lowland, intermediate and highland) of four regions (Amhara, Oromia, SNNP, Tigray) using a semi-structured questionnaire survey in 2014 reported losses in wheat along on the different post-harvest operations (harvesting (6.8–16.3%), threshing (3.5%), cleaning (2.1%), bagging (0.2%), transport from farm to store (1.1%) and store to market (0.2%), farm storage (2.7%), etc.) to be between 14 and 23%, the average being 17%. A higher loss figure was reported when there was rain at harvest. Losses due to post harvest disease may occur at any time during post-harvest handling, from harvest to consumption. Adugna and Kemal (1985) recorded thirty-six insect pest species, latter Abdurrahman and Adugna (1991) recorded 41 species and recently Bayeh *et al.*, 2008 reported 52 insect pests on wheat crop. This shows that in the last four decades the number of insect pest species that feed on wheat has been increasing. Moreover, the area under wheat has been increasing and the systems of production have diversified to include irrigation. The increased availability of the host plant contributes for a number of insect pest

species to shift their degree of importance and also new ones to appear. Therefore, this survey study designed to know the present status of insect pests of wheat at Arsi and west Arsi, south Eastern Ethiopia poetizing the following specific objectives.

Objective of the study

- Determination of current species composition of insect pests of wheat at different production season/mer, belg around Arsi and west Arsi.
- Assessments of relative importance and distribution of wheat insect pests at wheat stores level.
- Recommendation of wheat insect pest both at field and store level at different production seasons

Materials and methods

Description of the study area

Survey was conducted both at Arsi (Kulumsa, Dera, Abomsa, Chole, Sire, Arsi robe, Bekoji) and west Arsi (Asassa, Dodola, Kofele, Shashamene) conducted for two years from Sep.2019 up to July twice a year i.e. at mer and belg season.

Methodology

Field sampling was made during seedling/tillering and reproductive periods/flag leaf growth stage of wheat, whereas in stores it was carried out after harvest in store. Representative sample sites selected based on agro-ecological zones. Different types of sampling techniques also employed depending on the type of field insect pest present. For Field Survey Stops were be made at every 5 km interval along the main road to assess the surrounding fields. 30-50 sweeps were made in each farm walking across the field following the following routes. Route 1. Kulumsa → Dera → Abomsa → Chole → Sire → Arsi robe, Route2. Kulumsa → Bekoji → Asassa → Dodola → Kofele → Shashamene. In each sample site, 6-10 fields or store were selected and traced for the type and abundance of wheat insect pests. The eggs, larva, pupa and adult of field insect pests within 50cm X 50cm area at the middle of the field was observed in-situ and ex-situ for any type of parasitism and predation. For storage pests assessment about 250g grain collected per selected farm house and brought to laboratory for incubation period of 3 months and checked for adult pests emergence. The eggs, larva, pupa and adult of field insect pests observed in-situ and ex-situ for any type of parasitism and predation.

Collected data

Data collected for both field and storage insect pests of wheat includes; GPS data, geographical data, production history, insect pest injury %, stages of insect development, control measures practiced by farmer's, field /storage type conditions, specific niche of the insect pest/ part of the plant attacked, farmers' insect pest management practices and etc.

Table 1. Geographical coordinates of the survey area

SN	District	Latitude	Longitude
1	Dehera	7.0202038-7.031515	38.9571223-38.9979014
2	Hetosa	8.0870326-8.1424752	39.2228472-39.3191193
3	Kofale	7.0202038-7.031515	38.9571223-38.9979014
4	Adaba	7.0067949-7.0240699	39.3433441-39.4417384
5	Dodola	6.9826638-7.0087061	39.060788-39.1540921
6	Bekoji	7.2990412-7.6934489	39.1644805-39.2708657
7	Asasa	7.0381086-7.2838827	2385-2612
8	Kulumsa	8.0236981-8.0433893	39.1692391-39.1981914

Result discussion and Recommendation

Crop products are eventually stored for varied periods of time depending on market demand, size of production and the farmer's needs. Storage is the most important and critical post-harvest operation. Deterioration of the grain quality during storage can be due to improper storing conditions, which leads to contamination with fungi or insect infestation. Improper handling of crops during post-harvest processes can cause fungal infestation. Any damage to stored products increases their susceptibility to fungal contamination.

The storage microorganisms and pests cause economic losses in stored grains in many parts of the world. Pest survey: is an n official procedure conducted over a defined period of time to determine the characteristics of a pest population or to determine which pest species occur in an area. Assessments of Wheat insect pest are a key to investigate and predict new and existing losses at field and storage levels. As from survey done storage grains attacked granary weevil, *Sitophilus granarius* (L.); maize weevil, *Sitophilus zeamais* Motschulsky; *R. dominica*.

The loss is higher because the grain storage structures do not have adequate conservation properties. placing the wheat berries in an airtight, waterproof container in the freezer., cold temperature will kill any bugs or eggs, sealing wheat in Mylar-type bags or #10 cans along with appropriate number of oxygen absorber packets to create an oxygen-free atmosphere, will kill adult insects and prevent larval insects from surviving. Choose insect-free sources for wheat. Store them in clean and dry containers impermeable to insects. Use of most broad-spectrum, persistent insecticides (e.g. carbamates, organophosphates, pyrethroids) labeled for control of foliage-chewing insects. The use of the entomopathogenic fungus, *Metarhizium anisopliae*. Integrated Pest Management (IPM) is an effective and environmentally sensitive approach to pest management that relies on a combination of common-sense practices.

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